

Deliverable D7.4

Community engagement strategy (CES)

Deliverable report

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Document Contributors

Deliverable responsible	ZABALA	
Contributors	Organization	
Leire Martiarena	ZABALA	
Nahikari Diosdado	ZABALA	
Reviewers	Organization	
Lorena Viladés	ANEFA	
José Eugenio Ortiz	UPM-AI	
Max Pescher	CSI	
Paulo Romero	ANEFA	
Eduardo García	ZABALA	
Violeta Vázquez	ZABALA	

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Disclaimer

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CES	Community Engagement Strategy
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
RM	Raw Materials
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work Package
VICAT	Granulats Vicat
HANSON	Hanson Hispania
CIMPOR	AGREPOR AGREGADOS - EXTRACÇÃO DE INERTES
HOLCIM	HOLCIM AGGREGATI CALCESTRUZZI
CSI	Cronenberger Steinindustrie Franz Triches GmbH & Co.KG

1 Executive Summary

This document constitutes the **Deliverable D7.4 Community Engagement Strategy (CES) of the DIGIECOQUARRY project**. This deliverable corresponds to the Task 7.2 (Definition of the Community Engagement Strategy for every pilot site) of Work Package (WP) 7 Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers.

The Project INNOVATIVE DIGITAL SUSTAINABLE AGGREGATES SYSTEMS (H2020-SC5-2020-2) will exploit the aggregates industry's great potential through a coordinated approach towards construction materials management with the final goal of reducing EU external supply dependency as well as leading to an efficient use of resources. DIGIECOQUARRY will develop systems, technology and processes for integrated digitization and automation real-time process control, to be piloted in 5 EU quarries with the target of improving health and safety conditions for workers. The pilot campaigns will lead to improved efficiency of processes maximizing quarry resources and sustainable management of water, energy emissions, minimized environmental impact and expanding the EU aggregates and construction business. Coupling Artificial Intelligence approaches with cyber-physical systems and the Internet of Things concept, make Industry 4.0 approach possible and the smart sustainable extractive site a reality. All phases of the process, from extraction to the end user are covered by DIGIECOQUARRY, ensuring communication with policy makers, social awareness activities and international cooperation with the Colombia and South Africa partners to share knowledge and best practices. The development of an innovative Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS) will increase the sustainable supply of minerals for the construction sector as well as enabling the sustainable extraction of EU's mineral resources in existing and new quarries.

This Project includes 25 partners and will last for 48 months, starting on 1st June 2021. It is divided into 11 Work Packages. One of them is Work Package 7 (WP7), named Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers, which will cover the complete duration of the Project.

The main objective of WP7 is to establish mechanisms, tools and methodologies to build long-term and mutually benefitting relationships between quarries and local stakeholders, ensuring the **social awareness of raw materials and community understanding in the 5 pilot quarries**.

WP7 will work very close to the pilots in WP6 (and in line with WP9) to: (1) Ensure social awareness of raw materials; (2) Improve community understanding and deliver positive and effective outcomes for Raw Materials (RM) projects; (3) Integrate the 5 pilot sites involved with the local identity and values; (4) Include community perceptions in RM projects decision-making and design; (5) Build trust, relationships, feelings of ownership, and a sense of collaboration through the provision of meaningful and ongoing communication with local stakeholders and other policy makers; (6) Establish and develop dialogue processes with local communities; (7) Provide transparent and responsiveness access to project information and activities; (8) Define and implement one-way and two-way communication actions with policy makers.

This deliverable, elaborated under Task 7.2 Definition of the Community Engagement Strategy for every pilot site, is based on the stakeholder prioritisation and the social risks and individual needs identified in deliverables D7.1, D7.2 and D7.3, and comprises the Community Engagement Strategy (CES) for each pilot site, including the activities and tools necessary to carry out the proposed actions, as well as questionnaires and other required materials.

Deliverable D7.5 will collect the lessons learned and best practices obtained after the implementation of the CES actions (to be implemented from M25 until the end of the project), including the measurement of the impact of the different strategies.

2 Introduction and scope

The D7.4 deliverable is the second output of the task 7.2, the definition of the Community Engagement Strategy (CES) for every pilot site, run in the frame of WP7, Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers, led by ZABALA and involving the following other partners: ANEFA, VICAT, HANSON, HOLCIM, CSI, CIMPOR.

The **main objective of task 7.2** is to design a Community Engagement Strategy adapted each pilot site and includes the principles that guide the strategies, desired outcomes, as well as the specific methods of education and awareness raising activities with the local stakeholders.

In task 7.1 **ZABALA** built a **context narrative** for each pilot site and identified the **relevant stakeholders** of each pilot site, focusing on the local community and those with an interest in or influence on the project. Furthermore, **ZABALA** identified the main **potential risks in the extractive industry** at global level and based on this general risk identification and then identified the **key social risks in each pilot site** that could affect the DIGIECOQUARRY project development directly or indirectly through a consultation and validation process with pilot representatives (internal local stakeholders).

The identification of risks **developed in task 7.1** enabled to define the Communications and Social Awareness Plan (D7.3), where the priorities needed to design the Community Engagement Strategy (CES) present in this deliverable have been well established.

2.1 Relation to other activities and deliverables

WP7 is devoted to social awareness and interaction with policy makers to ensure social awareness of raw materials and promote best quarrying practices. This WP will get the local communities and the general public involved to define the future of the non-energy extractive sector under this new approach.

Thus, WP7 will work very close to **WP8** and **WP9**. WP7 will establish mechanisms, tools, and methodologies to ensure community understanding and awareness in the 5 pilot quarries (Fig. 1). WP8 will establish a powerful, solid network of stakeholders and WP9 will ensure dissemination and communication, including exploitation and business plan definition.

Social awareness, market uptake and management, will aim at developing and implementing the appropriate mechanisms for social awareness (WP7) joining forces and finding synergies with related projects and initiatives through tailored networking activities with key stakeholders at EU/world level (WP8), defining and undertaking communication and dissemination actions to maximise the project impact (WP9).

Figure 1 Relationship between WPs 7, 8 and 9

2.2 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the “Community Engagement Strategy” is structured as follows:

Section 1 – Executive summary: Contains a brief statement of the project.

Section 2 – Introduction and scope: Provides introductory information with respect to the Community Engagement Strategy and its structure as well as its scope and its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables.

Section 3 – Community Engagement Strategy (CES), methodology and tools in the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY: Introduces the background and rationale behind WP7, the principles for effective community engagement strategies, the tools and methodology that will be used for engagement and the monitoring of the community engagement strategy.

Section 4 – Community Engagement Strategy plan for each pilot site: Introduces the phases and the principal stakeholders of the Community Engagement Strategy as a whole. It also provides the community engagement strategy for each of the pilot sites, considering the specific physical and socioeconomical context, the characteristic of the quarry workers and the objectives for each quarry.

Section 5 – Conclusions: Pertains the main conclusions of the Community Engagement Strategy as well as the way forward.

3 Community Engagement Strategy (CES), methodology and tools in the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY

One of the main specific objectives of DIGIECOQUARRY is to foster social acceptance by introducing novel participatory processes and engagement actions with local communities and policy makers by **establishing a Community Engagement Strategy (CES) to ensure social awareness of raw materials** and improve public understanding and trust of the new quarrying technologies. As a result, the project will generate positive Environmental, Social, H&S and Economic impacts related to quarries, contributing to expand and strengthen the EU aggregates industry.

As part of the process to design the CES, deliverable D7.1 was addressed to understand the European Raw Materials sector and its key social risks as well as the local context and particularities of each pilot site. Furthermore, an identification of the main stakeholders was carried out for each pilot site, focusing on the local community and those with an interest in or influence on the project.

In deliverable D7.2, we have identified the key social risks in each pilot site, assessing their likelihood and impact, through a **participatory process (consultation and validation) with the pilot representatives** (internal stakeholders).

In deliverable D7.3, a compilation of social risks per quarry and the identification of stakeholders was made, necessary to establish priorities when designing the CES. The **CES will enable the project to mitigate these risks**, both those already existing in each of the quarries in their daily operations and the potential risks as a result of the implementation of the technology developed in the project.

The objective of the CES is to foster public participation and stakeholder involvement processes, transparency and information disclosure, and good and open communication, to increment the existing credibility, reliability, and acceptance, allowing ultimately to achieve **social awareness and understanding of raw materials with the local communities and stakeholders**.

Regarding social awareness and understanding, a survey for the members of the International Advisory Board (IAB) was prepared and commented on during the last meeting on March 6th, 2023, in order to collect their feedback about this and different topics of the project. The IAB is composed by relevant stakeholders of the aggregates value chain to provide external input, advice and feedback when the project is experiencing difficulties during its execution, and to provide valuable external input and feedback on project validation, replicability and up-scaling, transition to market and how to broaden the project's reach. Most of them are EU/international representatives or umbrella organisations: Global Aggregates Information Network (GAIN); International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN); Aggregates Business Europe (AggB); European Aggregates Association (UEPG); European Geological Surveys; Federal Association of Mineral Raw Materials (MIRO); European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OSHA).

A total of 11 members of the IAB participated anonymously through an online survey. The results of the survey are presented below (Fig. 2).

1.-How relevant is social acceptance for extractive industries?

2.-Please briefly explain why you selected the previous option. We want to better understand your perspective and opinions.

Currently, all administrative processes related to the authorization of mining industries are the subject of public information and consultations with "You have to take the local community with you. As much open dialogue, quarry site visits, visits to local schools as possible. The importance of quarr" "Without social acceptance there is no operation feasible "

3.-Which is the current level of social acceptance? In general, would you say the extractive industry is more accepted?

4.-Please briefly explain why you selected the previous option. We want to better understand your perspective and opinions.

"The bad social perception of the mining industry, derived from past times. This perception has been transferred to the new generations. It is very nec" "Some people understand the need to extract mineral products to sustain and enhance quality of life. Many do not fully see the link. They only see dirt" "Not in my back yard principle "

5.-What are the main barriers to gaining social acceptance?

6. Any other barrier that are relevant, and why?

7. What kind of actions can be taken to address the barriers you have identified? Which are the most effective? (Select the four you consider most effective)

8. Would you like to highlight any good practices to communicate and interact with local authorities and communities?
"1) Some type of local incentive: sports sponsorship, community gardens, cultural events, etc. that bring the industry closer to its immediate social en"

9. What is your opinion on the concept of social license to operate? Is it a useful tool?

10. In your experience, what are some of the key factors that contribute to employee acceptance of digitalization and procedure changes?

11.-What are the biggest barriers to gain the employees acceptance of digitalization and procedure changes?

12.-How can organizations improve their efforts to engage with and support their workers?

13.- Do you know any good practice in the sector to upskill and reskill employees, particularly as new technologies and practices continue to emerge?

“1) Continuous training 2) Incentives on positive results. (Nothing new)”

Figure 2 Results of survey related to social dimension shared by the members of the IAB.

Considering the information gathered in previous deliverables and taking into account the suggestions and comments provided by the members of the IAB, in this deliverable we will define the Community Engagement Strategy adapted to every pilot site including the principles that guide the strategies, desired outcomes, as well as the specific methods of engagement. It will also outline plans for dealing with issues and complaint processes, and how on-going evaluation of engagement will be done.

We will involve the local community of the pilot sites in the creation of the CES, with the aim of including community inputs in the process of developing the strategy. **A version of the strategy will be presented to the local stakeholders to ensure socialisation as well as providing an opportunity for feedback**, which will be validated through by local partners through a questionnaire sent to representatives of each community or through a focus group of local representatives.

3.1 Principles for effective Community Engagement Strategies

Community engagement offers numerous benefits and plays an essential role in empowering citizens and building stronger, more resilient communities. While the specific benefits and importance of community engagement vary depending on the context and the goals of the projects or initiatives, there are several key opportunities that are commonly identified.

One of the primary benefits of community engagement is that it increases the likelihood that the project will be widely accepted: when citizens participate in these processes, they show significant commitment to helping make them happen. This can result in greater support for the initiatives, as well as reduced resistance and opposition from community members.

Another key benefit is that community engagement creates more effective solutions. Drawing on local knowledge from a diverse group creates solutions that are practical and effective, tailored to the unique needs and challenges of the community. By involving a broad range of stakeholders in the decision-making process, community engagement helps to ensure that the new solutions are well-informed and meet the needs of all members of the community. In addition, community engagement empowers and integrates people from different backgrounds. Groups that feel ignored can gain greater control over their lives and their community, helping to build a sense of ownership and investment in the community's success and strengthening social cohesion. Community engagement also helps to increase citizen and stakeholder's trust. Working together improves communication and understanding, reducing the potential for conflicts and misunderstandings.

By building trust, creating a sense of ownership, and empowering stakeholders, organizations can ensure that the project is aligned with community values and expectations. This helps to reduce the risk of opposition and conflict and creates a foundation for successful and sustainable relationships in the future. To achieve this and ensure the success of the engagement process, there are some key principles that should be followed:

1. **Effective communication with the community in a reliable and understandable way:** The initial and one of the most important stages of community engagement is providing the public with accurate and complete information about the project and issues being discussed: it's essential that the public has the necessary knowledge to make informed decisions. To achieve this, it's important to use language that is easily understood and free of technical terms and jargon, and the communication should be designed to engage the public and make the topic of discussion relevant to their daily lives.
2. **A process that is transparent, consistent, and that clearly links the results of community engagement to the decision-making process:** To make community engagement effective, it is crucial to ensure transparency in the process. This means that the goals of the process must be clearly defined, achievable, and well-communicated to the public, and it is important to explain to stakeholders how their input will be taken into account when making decisions. Additionally, providing feedback to the participants is crucial as it shows that their opinions and contributions are valued.
3. **Acknowledgment of the knowledge and expertise of participants, and commitment to incorporating their feedback into the decision-making process:** When creating public engagement processes, it's crucial to recognize the valuable knowledge and experience that community members possess. Effective community engagement processes should allow community members to share their thoughts, opinions, ideas, and vision, as well as making sure they are considered when making decisions about the project and the issues being discussed.
4. **Inclusive participation by diverse and representative population groups (stakeholders):** This means that all relevant stakeholders, regardless of their background or status, should have the opportunity to participate in the decision-making process. For each of the pilot sites, an analysis of the stakeholders has already been conducted and is available in deliverable D7.3, considering their influence and interest/impact on each quarry. The matrixes created with this information will guide the engagement process. By involving a diverse and representative group of stakeholders, the engagement process can be more inclusive and effective, leading to better outcomes for everyone involved.

5. **Accessibility and social inclusivity, ensuring that all members of the community have an equal opportunity to participate:** When engaging with the public, it is crucial to ensure that everyone has the opportunity to participate, regardless of any physical or visual impairments they may have. This means providing facilities and amenities to accommodate people with disabilities, such as wheelchair ramps, accessible washrooms, and designated parking spaces, if needed for in person meeting and activities. It is also important to make presentations and written materials such as leaflets, forms and Power Point presentations visually appealing and easy to read. The goal is to make the engagement process as accessible as possible so that everyone in the community can have a say.

3.2 Tools and methodology for engagement

For effective engagement in each of our pilots, engagement methods and tools that are most appropriate for each quarry will be used, based on the stakeholder prioritisation and the social risks identified in previous deliverables (D7.1, D7.2, D7.3).

While the tools used may differ for each pilot, we have identified several common ones that will be utilized considering the characteristics of the project, to ensure that engagement with participants is effective and that their knowledge is applied throughout the project. By tailoring our engagement methods to each pilot, we can ensure that our engagement efforts are successful and that the needs of each community are met.

It is important to understand why these tools are being used and how they can be useful for achieving the project's goals. Each tool has its own strengths and limitations and may be more or less effective depending on the context and the goals of the engagement effort. In the table below you will find a variety of tools, their description and how they will be used within the framework of the project's community engagement strategy:

Table 1 Tools for community engagement strategy.

Tool	Description	Use
Surveys	Useful for gathering information from specific stakeholders. There are different types of surveys, such as web-based, telephone, mail out, in-person interviews... and are useful for collecting data, feedback, and opinions from the community.	To ensure a meaningful and effective citizen engagement process, we will be conducting surveys to gather feedback and insights from members of the community, as well as from the pilot quarries, to see how the changes are affecting the workers. These surveys will also assess the level of awareness, attitudes, trust, satisfaction, and knowledge among the community regarding the project.
Leaflets	Leaflets are commonly used to convey information or promote a specific project, service, or event. They are designed to be eye-catching and easy to read, with key information presented in a clear and concise manner. They can be distributed in a variety of ways, including through direct mail/email, and hand-to-hand distribution.	Leaflets can be used to inform about upcoming events and provide updates on project progress. It is important to ensure that the information presented is accurate, relevant, and presented in a way that is accessible and easy to understand for the target audience by using simple language. We will provide the community with an understanding of the project's goals and objectives, as well as updates on any changes or developments, using this tool.
News in media	Information that is disseminated through various forms of media, such as newspapers, television, radio, and online platforms, among others.	News in media will be used to inform the public about project updates, events, and other important information. This will include press releases, news articles, and other forms of media outreach to keep the community and stakeholders informed and engaged. By publishing news in media, we can reach a wide audience and ensure that accurate and up-to-date information is shared with the community.
Mailings	Mailing refers to the distribution of electronic mail, or emails, to a specific group of people. In the context of a project, mailing can be used as a tool for communication and engagement with stakeholders, community members, and project participants.	Mailing lists can be created to reach out to specific groups or individuals and provide updates, information, and invitations to participate in project-related events and activities. Withing the Community engagement strategy, mailing will be used to keep in touch with customers, suppliers, and investors.
Site Tours and Open Days	An organized tour or open days involve not only viewing the sites, but also discussions and question and answer sessions about the site plans and updates on the projects being carried out, which gives a good opportunity to obtain feedback from community members.	As part of the community engagement strategy for the project, there will be open days and site visits to the quarries to showcase any changes or new technologies that have been implemented. These events will provide an opportunity for community members to see the project progress and to ask questions or provide feedback. By opening the sites

		to the public, we hope to build trust and foster transparency with the community.
Training sessions	Training sessions are structured sessions designed to provide participants with knowledge and skills relevant to a particular topic or activity.	Training sessions will be provided to relevant stakeholders, including coordinators of the quarries and their communication teams, to ensure that they have the necessary knowledge and skills. The ones prepared for the coordinators of the quarries will focus on knowledge about the project, its goals and the changes that come with it, to ensure that they are well-equipped to communicate with the quarry workers and address any concerns or questions that may arise, especially regarding the work they are doing in the quarries and how it may be affected.
Posters	Visual displays that provide concise and easy-to-understand information about a specific topic. Posters can be used to communicate project goals and outcomes in a clear and engaging way, useful to share important information, and educate the community about the project and its impact.	Posters are a great way to reach a large audience and can be placed in high-traffic areas such as community centers, libraries, and public buildings, as well as in the pilot quarries so all employees always have the necessary information available. They can also be shared digitally through social media and project websites to increase visibility and accessibility.
Workshops	In a workshop, a group of people come together to collaborate on an issue and create solutions. They can be formal or informal, and often involve sharing information on a specific topic and encouraging group discussions.	Workshops stimulate discussion and encourage creative thinking around a particular topic or issue. They also provide an opportunity for participants to be actively involved in problem-solving and decision-making. Whiting the project and the community engagement strategies for each pilot site, diverse workshops will take place, especially workshops focused on informing and helping workers to navigate the new technologies and changes implemented in the quarries as a result of DEQ.
Dossiers for public administration	A dossier for public administration is a collection of documents that provide detailed information about a project or initiative. It typically includes background information, objectives, timelines, impacts on the community and other relevant details.	They will be used as a reference for public administration and stakeholders who need to understand the project and its implications. In the context of citizen engagement, a well-prepared dossier can help to build trust and credibility with the public and demonstrate transparency and commitment to open communication.
Meetings with stakeholders	These meetings are designed to gather feedback and ideas from stakeholders and involve them in the project.	Throughout the project, there will be several meetings with stakeholders to discuss important topics related to the quarries, the project, and the

		community engagement strategy. These sessions will also provide an opportunity to showcase any new changes, technologies or initiatives that have been implemented and allow stakeholders to ask questions and provide input.
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3.3 Monitoring of the community engagement strategy

Since community engagement work involves many variables, it is important to closely monitor and evaluate the approach taken. Undertaking evaluations of a community engagement process is key to understand what was done well and what could be improved upon in the future, so the developed strategy for each quarry will be closely monitored throughout its implementation to ensure its effectiveness. In order to develop an effective community engagement strategy, it also is important to take into account the engagement activities that are already being carried out in the quarry sites.

Yearly evaluations will be conducted to assess the strategy's strengths and weaknesses and make any necessary adjustments. This ongoing monitoring will enable us to identify areas of success and areas for improvement and will ultimately help to ensure that the strategy is achieving its intended outcomes and ensure that the needs of the stakeholders are met.

One of the challenges is to monitor and measure these activities, as it has not been done before. Therefore, in the development of the community engagement strategy, we will be placing a strong emphasis on monitoring and evaluating the engagement activities that have been implemented in the past and that are being repeated, as well as those that will be developed in the future. By doing this, we will be able to ensure that the engagement activities are effective and aligned with the goals of the project, and that they are meeting the needs of the stakeholders.

The monitoring will help to identify which activities are working well and which are not and will allow for adjustments to be made to improve the overall effectiveness of the strategy. **ZABALA** will lead the monitoring effort throughout the duration of the DIGIECOQUARRY project, and quarries will be trained on how to monitor their own engagement activities effectively during the project and beyond. This will ensure that they are able to continue monitoring their activities and community engagement once the project has ended, using the monitoring data to continuously improve engagement activities and ensure that they remain relevant for stakeholders.

To assess the effectiveness of the community engagement strategy for each quarry, specific questionnaires will be administered at the beginning and end of the community engagement activities planned within the development of the project, as well in the beginning and the end of each phase of the community engagement strategy, specifically at the beginning and end of each cycle (year 1 and year 2), as is it explained in section 4. These questionnaires will measure variables such as awareness, attitude, trust, satisfaction, knowledge, and behavioural change, to determine the impact of the engagement strategy and identify areas for improvement.

The best practices identified through the community engagement strategy will not only be beneficial for the quarry sites involved in this project but could also be applied to other quarry sites in the future. The sharing of successful engagement strategies and activities across the industry will help improve overall community relations, ensure social awareness of raw materials, and promote a positive image of the quarrying industry.

These are the variables that will be measured through questionnaires at the beginning and end of a community engagement strategy cycle to assess its effectiveness:

1. **Awareness:** to measure how much the community knows about the project.
2. **Attitude:** to gauge the community's opinions and perceptions about the project.
3. **Trust:** to measure how much the community trusts the quarry they are engaging with.
4. **Satisfaction:** to measure the community's satisfaction with the engagement process and outcomes.
5. **Knowledge:** to measure how much the community learned through the engagement process.
6. **Behavioural change:** to determine whether the engagement strategy led to any changes in the community's behaviour related to the quarries, considering the changes observed in the other five variables.

In addition to the use of questionnaires to measure the effectiveness of our community engagement strategy, a seventh variable, (7) **Participation**, will be tracked based on the number of individuals involved in the process. This will include attendance at meetings, events, and other engagement activities. By tracking participation, we can determine the level of community involvement and assess the reach of our engagement efforts.

It is also important to mention that, within the monitoring of the strategy, the data collection process that will be carried out as part of the community engagement strategy will also be integrated into the online platform that is being developed in WP4. This will provide a comprehensive view of the community engagement efforts and their impact.

The monitoring phase will also follow up on the resources needs to implement different engagement strategies to conduct a cost-efficiency analysis. This will allow to analyse the performance of the different actions according to their impact and the allocation of budget for these actions, prioritising those offering more value to improve community relationships.

4 Community Engagement Strategy for each pilot site

In this section we will provide the Community Engagement Strategy for each pilot site. The overall objective of this strategy is to foster meaningful and inclusive participation from community members and stakeholders. By involving a broad range of voices and perspectives, the strategy aims to build trust, create a sense of ownership and investment, and empower citizens to help shaping the projects and initiatives in their community. The strategy recognizes the importance of community engagement in building stronger and more resilient communities and seeks to leverage the numerous benefits that engagement can offer, including increased support, more effective solutions, and greater social cohesion.

The Community Engagement Strategy is also important for ensuring that the DEQ project is accepted and successful. By involving local communities and stakeholders in the decision-making process and addressing their concerns and needs, we can increase the likelihood of project success and reduce the risk of opposition or conflicts. Moreover, in the long run, these strategies will help to improve the image of quarries and the mining industry in general by demonstrating a commitment to social responsibility and sustainability.

The proposal of the communication approaches and activities suggested for each quarry are based on the **stakeholder classification** obtained in deliverable 7.1 and on the **evaluation of social risks** of each quarry developed in deliverable 7.2, and the **Communications and Social Awareness Plan** and activities for each quarry 7.3.

Furthermore, to ensure the achievement of the CES goals in each pilot site, it is important to take into account that each quarry has its own relationship dynamics with stakeholders developed throughout the life of the quarries, so each engagement plan is based on the quarry's own engagement and communication strategies and channels.

Thus, the DEQ project will complement and strengthen, and in some cases formalize and procedure, the already existing engagement actions. When needed, it will also help formalize them in structured plans with monitoring indicators that will allow the quarries to implement these once the project ends and measure its effectiveness. The project also provides the opportunity to exchange strategies and actions, enriching them with the experience gained from other pilots' practices. Therefore, although the CES pursues a common goal for the project, each quarry will conduct the engagement strategy that best suits them.

After the implementation of the CES (between M25 and the end of the project), the final deliverable *D7.5 Social Understanding* will describe all the CES actions conducted in the different pilots throughout the project, and their impact and effectiveness will be measured. This will allow us to extract lessons learned and best practices from each pilot site and propose some recommendations and guidelines for designing new CES. This, in turn, will serve as an example for other quarries in the sector to create and implement their own strategies.

Therefore, and as it was done with the activities proposed in the communication plans, **the methodology and strategies present in each community engagement strategy have been reviewed and approved following each quarries/companies' communication and relationships strategies and policies**, and all the proposed actions will be continuously updated to ensure their effectiveness. It is important to highlight that the planning has been checked with every quarry, as well as every company's communication department and adapted to their schedules, plans and existing communication strategies and plans.

Phases of the Community Engagement Strategy

The community engagement strategy will be implemented in two phases: (1) a **consolidation and exploration phase** and a (2) **co-creation and deepening phase**. These phases will be cyclical, especially the second one, which will not end once completed: it will continue to be improved over the years, building upon what has been done and the information that has been gathered in the consolidation phase.

The specific timing of the activities within each cycle will be determined based on the optimal moments for carrying them out and will aim to create synergies with other stakeholder activities. This means there are no fixed dates for when the engagement activities in each of the phases will take place, as their timing will be guided by the needs and interests of stakeholders, as well as external events that may impact engagement efforts: flexibility is key to ensuring that the strategy is effective and responsive to local conditions.

PHASE 1: CONSOLIDATION AND EXPLORATION PHASE

The primary objective of the first phase of the Community Engagement Strategy is to establish a foundation of trust and transparency between the project team and the stakeholders. Based on the context and risk analysis, this phase will go deeper in the "State of the Art" and will integrate the view of a more diverse variety of stakeholders. Using this information, the project team can identify gaps in communication and engagement and develop a tailored approach to address them.

One of the key activities during this phase is to provide accurate and complete information about the project and the issues being discussed to the public. This includes engaging with internal and external stakeholders, including public authorities and diverse community members, to ensure that they have the necessary knowledge to make informed decisions. This will involve a range of activities such as open days, stakeholder meetings, and other forms of engagement that provide opportunities for the public to ask questions and express their opinions.

Another important objective of the first phase is to identify the specific needs and demands of stakeholders and the community in relation to the project. This information will be used to develop targeted engagement activities and ensure that the project team is responsive to the community's needs and concerns. By the end of the first year, the project team will evaluate the effectiveness of the engagement activities and identify opportunities for improvement.

Overall, the first phase of the Community Engagement Strategy is focused on building a strong foundation of trust and transparency, providing accurate and complete information, and identifying the specific needs and demands of stakeholders and the community. This will set the stage for the more collaborative and co-creative activities of the second phase.

Of course, each pilot site has unique characteristics and challenges, which means that the community engagement activities and methods will vary depending on the context and information gathered in the previous deliverables (D7.1, D7.2, and D7.3). By tailoring the approach to each pilot site, we can ensure that the community engagement addresses the specific needs and concerns of each quarry.

After the completion of phase one, a comparative analysis will be conducted to assess the effectiveness of the engagement strategy in achieving its objectives in comparison with the state of the art gathered at the beginning.

PHASE 2: CO-CREATION AND DEEPENING PHASE

During the second phase of the Community Engagement Strategy, the focus will be on co-creation, building on the foundation established during the first year to deepen the relationship with stakeholders. The co-creation and deepening phase will build on this foundation by engaging stakeholders in a more participatory and collaborative process, focused on generating new ideas and strengthening relationships. The information gathered in phase 1 will help us to see which activities work, which are more interesting for the stakeholders, and which are, in general, more suitable for each of the quarries. Through this iterative approach, the community engagement strategy will be refined and improved over time, ensuring that it continues to meet the needs and aspirations of all stakeholders.

One of the main objectives of this phase is to ensure social awareness or raw materials and improve community understanding, which involves building trust, ensuring transparency, and demonstrating a commitment to environmental and social responsibility, so that the stakeholders accept not only the DIGIECOQUARRY project, but also the work being done in the quarries. Overall, the aim is to improve the social awareness of the quarries and the project, by building stronger relationships with stakeholders, demonstrating the benefits of the project, and addressing any negative perceptions or misconceptions. The specific activities undertaken during the second year will also be adapted to circumstances of each quarry, taking into account the information gathered in the previous deliverables (D7.1, D7.2, and D7.3), the input of key stakeholders collected in phase one, the specific risks and challenges faced by each quarry during the consolidation phase, and any existing activities or initiatives they have in place.

The cyclical nature of phase two of the community engagement strategy means that the engagement activities will not be a one-time event, but rather an ongoing process that is continuously improving over time, building upon the activities that were carried out in phase one and the data gathered from then. It is critical to ensure that the engagement remains active and sustained even after the project's completion, and that the strategies are adjusted as needed to ensure that they remain relevant and effective. This cyclical approach allows for continued collaboration with stakeholders and ensures that the community's concerns and needs are being met in the long term. This way, phase 2 will focus on continuous engagement beyond the end of the project and will aim to maintain the momentum and ensure that the social awareness and understanding of the quarries and project are sustained in the long term.

Principal stakeholders of the Community Engagement Strategy

The selection of stakeholders has been done considering the risk analysis conducted in the previous deliverables. The risks identified in the five different contexts of the DIGIECOQUARRY project are mainly related to the safety and health of workers, as well as the communities affected by mining. In addition, there are also significant bureaucratic challenges that affect the quarrying industry, such as the process of obtaining new permits and complying with new legislation at both the national and EU levels. These challenges can act as barriers to the continuation of quarries' activities and are therefore important to consider when assessing risks. The stakeholders selected for the Community Engagement Strategy have been prioritized based on their potential impact on these risks. Local authorities and policy makers, communities, and businesses in the vicinity of the quarries are key stakeholders, as they are affected by the operations of the quarries.

Based on this analysis, there are two main groups of stakeholders that are going to be prioritized in the Community Engagement Strategy: **internal and external stakeholders**. By prioritizing the needs and concerns

of both internal and external stakeholders, we can create a strategy that is effective, sustainable, and responsive to the needs of all parties involved.

Table 2 Main groups of stakeholders.

Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
<p>Internal stakeholders play a critical role in the success of the Community Engagement Strategy. Quarry workers are the backbone of the internal stakeholders, as they are directly involved in the operations related to the project. It is essential to engage with them, listen to their feedback, and address any concerns they may have.</p> <p>It is important to consider that the project will change the way they work; therefore, it is crucial to keep the workers well-informed about any changes and provide them with the necessary training and support to adapt to new work processes. By doing so, we can ensure that they are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to carry out their work effectively and efficiently while also minimizing any potential risks or challenges that may arise. WP9 of the project will include a strong emphasis on ensuring that the quarry workers are fully involved and engaged in the process of capacity building.</p> <p>In addition to workers, investors, suppliers, and clients are also considered relevant internal stakeholders in some quarries.</p>	<p>Includes the local communities and authorities, as well as the wider audience. The communities living in the vicinity of the quarries, local authorities, and other businesses in the area play a critical role in ensuring that the project and the quarries have social awareness and community understanding and receives the necessary support.</p> <p>It is important to engage with them to build trust, ensure transparency, and address any concerns or issues that may arise in the communities.</p> <p>Depending on the location and characteristics of the quarry, different external stakeholders may play a more significant role than others. For quarries located in urban areas, the involvement of citizens and local businesses is crucial, as they are near the quarry and may be impacted by its operations. On the other hand, quarries located in more rural areas may rely heavily on the support and cooperation of local authorities. Obtaining necessary permits and approvals may be more difficult in these areas, and it is important to engage with the relevant authorities in order to ensure that the project and the quarry operation can proceed smoothly.</p>

4.1 Community Engagement Strategy - VICAT

Physical and socioeconomical context

The FENOUILLET quarry is an urban treatment plant spanning over 46 000 m² that was originally built in 1970 on the outskirts of Toulouse. It is now situated in the middle of a bustling commercial area that boasts a civic centre, restaurants, and stores such as Decathlon, McDonald's, and Burger King. The municipality is part of the Toulouse living area, which is home to one million inhabitants.

The FENOUILLET quarry has no extraction site linked to it. Instead, the site recovers raw materials from local earthworks and acts as a recipient of construction and demolition waste, treating and supplying it as fill material to another concrete plant on the same site and to customers. Its strategic location allows for continuous inflows and outflows of aggregates, making it a crucial player in the circular economy in the field of building and public works.

What sets this quarry apart from other similar facilities is its location, which is very rare for a large recycling platform in the immediate vicinity of a large urban centre. Moreover, the quarry is committed to minimizing the visual impact produced by the plant and has erected earth walls planted with trees and reconditioned a small lake within the limits of the exploitation site.

Considering the proximity of the FENOUILLET quarry to the city and its thriving commercial area, it is crucial to consider the surrounding businesses and the community when implementing a community engagement strategy. Opportunities to collaborate and participate in activities with the neighbouring businesses should be explored to foster a strong relationship with the community and maximize the positive impact of the quarry's operations.

Quarry workers

The worker profile at FENOUILLET quarry is crucial to consider when planning the training and upskilling initiatives related to the DIGIECOQUARRY project. The quarry currently employs a total of 5 workers, consisting of 3 males and 2 females. Among them, 3 workers are in the age range of 16 to 25 years old, reflecting a younger demographic within the workforce. Additionally, there is one worker between 36 and 40 years old, and another worker aged between 41 and 45. In terms of education, 3 workers have a basic level of education, 1 has completed high school, and 1 has undergone an apprenticeship program.

Digital literacy skills are also relevant for the integration of new technologies. Among the workers, 3 possess basic digital skills, while 2 workers demonstrate intermediate proficiency in this area. These varying levels of digital literacy underscore the need for tailored training programs to ensure that all workers are equipped with the necessary skills to adapt to the changes brought by the project. By considering these worker demographics, educational backgrounds, and digital literacy levels, the training programs and materials can be designed to effectively address the specific needs and abilities of the FENOUILLET quarry workers, enabling a smoother transition and facilitating the successful implementation of the changes.

Regarding the changes made to the quarry within the work frame of DIGIECOQUARRY, it is important to note that the introduction of new technology will not replace the tasks previously carried out by employees, so they do not pose potential risks or negative impacts on employment or job security. On the contrary, it will facilitate the enhancement of personnel and property safety, as well as improvements in working conditions. Furthermore, there are health and safety benefits associated with the project's implementation at the quarry, including restricted access to certain hazardous areas of the production unit.

Objectives

Internal Stakeholders

- To ensure no resistance to change in the quarry and establish a communication pathway to prevent this from happening among employees.
- Introduce the project and explain the main goals, benefits, activities, and timeframe to coordinators and managers.
- Provide training and resources to workers to prepare them for changes in their work processes resulting from the project.

- Engage with workers to gather feedback and address any concerns they may have about the project including suggestions to improve tested solutions.
- Collaborate with investors to ensure their needs and concerns are met.
- Keep clients and suppliers informed of the project benefits, progress and any changes that may impact them.

External Stakeholders

- Collaborate and consult with local public administrations to ensure compliance with all relevant regulations and laws.
- Keep public administrations informed about the benefits of the project at local, regional and national level and find synergies with development plans and strategies.
- Engage with local communities to inform them about the project, address any concerns they may have, and gather feedback; inform about the project and potential impacts and benefits.
- Build strong relationships with local communities and address their needs and concerns.
- Present and communicate the renovation actions taken to minimize its environmental and visual impact in the quarry area, supported by the actions developed under the project.
- Raise awareness on the benefits of the plant for local communities.

Community Engagement Strategy – VICAT

PHASE 1: CONSOLIDATION AND EXPLORATION PHASE

Internal Stakeholders

During phase one, VICAT will be mainly focused on presenting the project at internal and external level. Internally, actions will be addressed to coordinators and managers to introduce the project and explain the main goals, benefits, activities, and timeframe. In addition, they will learn the sustainability benefits that the project will generate (environmental, economic, social) in relation to the sustainability policies and trends that are taking place within the extractive sector at EU level, including the 2030 Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Once the managers and coordinators learn about the project and its implications, they will be able to communicate it to the employees, who will get familiar with it through the regular internal meetings. Furthermore, the Commercial, Marketing and Communication departments will be trained on the project and the benefits and implications for the future sustainability of the extractive industry, so that clients, investors, and suppliers get relevant and accurate information on the project.

It will be also important to explain the implications in relation to the new requirements, standards and policies addressed to suppliers and clients related to sustainability within the quarry's supply chain because of the DIGIECOQUARRY project. These new policies will be also relevant for investors who integrate sustainability issues into their investing criteria.

Community Engagement activities for workers:

- Regular updates on the project during health and safety internal meetings with employees.
- Training workshops/capacity building: training and resources to help workers understand new technologies or equipment that will be introduced as part of the project.
- Inform workers about the DIGIECOQUARRY project and set the basis for bi-directional communication.
- Development of poster/communication material about the project to inform employees.
- Based on the monitoring strategy for the engagement strategy, establishing a system to gather feedback from workers, address any concerns they may have and ensure they feel valued and heard.
- Train the commercial/marketing/communications departments on the project and benefits for the future sustainability of the business activity.

Community Engagement activities for other internal stakeholders:

- Collaborate with investors and inform them about the benefits of DIGIECOQUARRY for the future sustainability of the business activity – potential sustainable supply chain requirements/policy as a result of the project.
- Inform clients about the benefits of DIGIECOQUARRY in the final product and about the sustainable supplier requirements/policy as a result of the project.
- Inform about the project and potential new sustainability requirements that may be required to suppliers.
- Dedicated news on the quarry website for suppliers and other internal stakeholders.
- Update of the supplier policy document if necessary.

External stakeholders

At external level, VICAT has been undertaking several actions to minimize its environmental and visual impact in the area. Furthermore, the company is undertaking a great rehabilitation plan both in the Fenouillet and Carbonne quarries where land walls are being built, trees are being planted, and a number of energy and water efficient measures are being undertaken. In addition, the Carbonne quarry was conditioned with a lake that hosts a restaurant and water adventure activities for the local communities. One of the objectives of the first phase will be focused on presenting and communicating these renovation actions supported by the actions developed under the DIGIECOQUARRY project by organising open door events addressed to public authorities and the general public, especially the neighbouring businesses and local residents. In addition, dedicated meetings and site visits with the City Council to update on the DIGIECOQUARRY project progress will be also conducted.

Community Engagement activities for Local Authorities:

- The quarry will consult and collaborate with the public administrations, keeping them informed about the benefits of the project at the local level and finding synergies with development plans and strategies.
- Elaboration of a communication dossier, with specific information of projects' impact in the territory.

- Organisation of an open-door event to present the new plant and the project implications and benefits.
- Meetings with City Council to update on project progress.

Community Engagement activities for Local Communities:

- Appoint a local community relations manager for contact with local communities.
- Organisation of Open-door events to present the new plant and the project impacts and benefits.
- Elaboration of leaflets or postcards explaining the project and new extraction techniques.
- Publication of a news article in the regional media to inform the local communities about the DIGIECOQUARRY project.

PHASE 2: CO-CREATION AND DEEPENING PHASE

In the second phase of VICAT's Community Engagement Strategy they will focus on maintaining and improving the activities that have been successful in phase 1. During this second phase, the entire marketing and communications team at VICAT will have already completed their training on the project and the engagement strategy. They will be ready to continue the quarry's engagement efforts, as they will have a solid understanding of the project's objectives and have established relationships with stakeholders during the first phase. This way, the team will be well-equipped to maintain effective communication and collaboration throughout the co-creation and deepening phase, and VICAT will continue to work closely with external stakeholders, including citizens and businesses in the surrounding areas, as well as local authorities, to co-create solutions that address their needs and concerns.

To foster a sense of ownership and commitment to the project's success, co-creation workshops will be organized where stakeholders can provide their feedback and ideas in an interactive and inclusive manner. The following activities will be carried out during this phase, subject to feedback and success from phase 1:

- Co-creation workshops: Inclusive and collaborative workshops will be organized for stakeholders to share their ideas and feedback.
- Site visits: Stakeholders will be invited to visit the quarry site and address any concerns or questions they may have.
- Stakeholder meetings: Two meetings a year will be held with stakeholders to keep them informed about the project's progress and address any new concerns or issues.
- Simple informative activities: Informative activities will be carried out to provide updates about the project's progress to internal and external stakeholders.

By engaging with stakeholders in this manner, VICAT aims to ensure that the engagement plan remains effective and responsive to stakeholders' needs. The activities carried out during this phase will deepen the relationship with stakeholders and foster a sense of community ownership and commitment to the project's success.

4.2 Community Engagement Strategy – HANSON

Physical and socioeconomical context

Given the physical and socio-economic context of the quarry (available in deliverable D7.1), there will be several aspects to consider withing the community engagement strategy:

- Altitude and climate: Being located at an altitude of about 800 meters above sea level, the quarry may face challenges such as extreme temperatures, strong winds, or snowfall during the winter months. It also has a typical Mediterranean climate, which can be characterized by extreme temperatures and strong drought periods during the summer months. It is important to consider these factors when planning community engagement activities, especially for outdoor events. It may be necessary to provide adequate facilities and measures to ensure the safety and comfort of the participants, such as shaded areas, water stations, or dust control measures. This also means that any outdoor community engagement activities, such as site visits or open days, should be planned accordingly and scheduled during the most suitable seasons to ensure the safety and comfort of the participants.
- Population centers: The closest population centre to the quarry is the town of Valdilecha, which is about 1,800 meters away. The town has a growing population, and it is important to engage with the local community to ensure that they are informed about the project, its benefits, and potential impacts. This will be done through various means, such as organizing meetings with local authorities or hosting open events for the community.

Overall, understanding these characteristics can help to design a community engagement strategy that is tailored to the specific needs and concerns of the stakeholders, and that takes into account the unique features of the quarry's location and surroundings.

In the case of Valdilecha it is important to highlight that due to the change of ownership of the HANSON quarry and with the purpose of not causing any detriment between the stakeholders and the new owners of the quarry, Valdilecha will maintain a low degree of interaction with the local stakeholders during transfer of ownership. This means that stakeholder engagement activities have been put on hold while the change of ownership takes place. This pause should not affect the CEQ: once the transfer is completed, the CES actions will be validated with the new company and the engagement activities will be implemented accordingly.

Quarry workers

The HANSON quarry has a total of 21 employees, all of them men and mostly over the age of 40. It is worth noting that 18 of them only have basic education, and more than half of them (14) have a very limited or basic technological level, meaning that, overall, the quarry workers have low level of digital literacy. This means that it is important to consider their age and technological proficiency when developing strategies to inform and educate them about the DIGIECOQUARRY project.

To ensure effective communication and engagement with the quarry workers, it will be necessary to provide them with training and information that is accessible and easy to understand, using methods that are suitable for their age and technological capabilities. This may include interactive workshops, training sessions, and

practical demonstrations of the new technologies and tools that will be used in the quarry. Additionally, regular updates and feedback sessions will be held with the workers, to ensure that they feel informed and involved in the project. It will also be important to address any concerns or difficulties they may have, and to provide support and guidance as needed.

Overall, the community engagement strategy for the HANSON quarry should prioritize the effective communication and engagement of its workers, considering their unique characteristics and needs. By doing so, they can ensure that the project is implemented successfully and that all stakeholders are informed and engaged throughout the process.

Objectives

Internal Stakeholders

- To ensure no resistance to change in the quarry and establish a communication pathway to prevent this from happening among employees.
- Provide training and resources to workers to prepare them for changes in their work processes resulting from the project.
- Engage with workers to gather feedback and address any concerns they may have about the project.
- Collaborate with investors to ensure their needs and concerns are met.
- Keep clients and suppliers informed of project progress and any changes that may impact them.

External Stakeholders

- Collaborate and consult with local and regional public administrations to ensure compliance with all relevant regulations and laws.
- Engage with local communities to inform them about the project, address any concerns they may have, and gather feedback.
- Build strong relationships with local communities and address their needs and concerns.

Community Engagement Strategy – HANSON-VALDILECHA

PHASE 1: CONSOLIDATION AND EXPLORATION PHASE

Internal Stakeholders

As the backbone of the quarries, the workers play a critical role in the operations and management of the project. HANSON will collaborate with them to ensure their safety and well-being and address any concerns they may have. Regular updates on the project will be provided during health and safety meetings with employees, and training and tools will be provided to help them carry out their work more safely and effectively. At the same time, the quarry will maintain contact with its clients and suppliers and collaborate with its investors, ensuring their involvement in the project and addressing their needs and concerns.

Community Engagement activities for workers:

- Regular updates on the project during health and safety internal meetings with employees.
- Training workshops/capacity building: training and resources to help workers understand new technologies or equipment that will be introduced as part of the project.
- Based on the monitoring strategy for the engagement strategy, establishing a system to gather feedback from workers, address any concerns they may have and ensure they feel valued and heard.

Community Engagement activities for other internal stakeholders:

- With investors, The HANSON quarry will inform about the benefits of DEQ for the future sustainability of the business activity, always aligned with their investment priorities.
- Clients will be informed about the benefits of DEQ in the final product, always aligned with their business priorities, using existing communication channels, such as using mailing.
- Creation of dedicated leaflets/diagram to informing about the innovations of the project and its consequences in the business development.
- Dedicated news on the quarry website for suppliers and other internal stakeholders.
- Update of the supplier policy document if necessary.

External stakeholders

To ensure that the project meets the community's needs and aligns with local development plans, the quarry will consult and collaborate with the public administrations. This will involve sharing information about the project and its benefits, as well as finding synergies with development plans and strategies. A dedicated dossier will be developed, and the quarry will engage with the local communities by informing them about the project and its potential impacts, organising activities and open days for the community, as well as offering information via local media. Considering that there are several of the improvements derived from DEQ that cannot be seen in person (such as, for example, the new blasting procedures), informative events will also be planned in which videos and photographs will be shown with information about the improvements.

Community Engagement activities for Local Authorities:

- The quarry will consult and collaborate with the public administrations, keeping them informed about the benefits of the project at the local level and finding synergies with development plans and strategies.
- A dedicated dossier with information about the project will be developed.

Community Engagement activities for Local Communities:

- The quarry will inform the local communities about the project and its potential impacts.
- Organisation of Tree Day Celebration for schoolchildren.

- Organisation of Open Doors Day for schoolchildren.
- Organisation of Open Doors Day for all residents of the community of Madrid, perhaps on the International Day for Mine Awareness and Assistance in Mine Action (4 of April).
- Events open to the public and local authorities so that they can view videos of the new processes and receive information about improvements to the quarry.
- Publication of a •to inform the local communities about the DIGIECOQUARRY project.

Open days and informative events will be of special importance to make a first contact with the local community. These events will be used to talk about what aspects that interest or concern them the most, as well as to create a first contact and invite them to continue participating in the activities that will continue to be carried out.

PHASE 2: CO-CREATION AND DEEPENING PHASE

The second phase of the Community Engagement Strategy is the Co-creation and Deepening Phase. During this phase, HANSON will engage in close collaboration with stakeholders to co-create solutions that address their needs and concerns. This phase aims to deepen the relationship with stakeholders and foster a sense of ownership and commitment to the project's success.

The focus for the activities of this phase will be to build upon the ones that have been carried out and monitored in phase 1. The connections established with stakeholders during the first phase will make it easier to involve them in this next stage, and co-creation workshops will be organized to allow stakeholders to provide their feedback and ideas in an interactive and inclusive manner. In the specific case of the Valdilecha quarry, most of the actions to establish a first communication with the local and regional authorities will take place in this phase: it must be considered that there will be a change of ownership in the quarry, so it is important that the new management established contact with local and regional authorities once the ownership change is complete.

The following is a summary of the activities that will continue to be carried out, although always subject to the feedback and the success of the activities carried out during the first phase and adapted to the lessons learned.

- Co-creation workshops: Stakeholders will be invited to participate in workshops where they can share their ideas and feedback. These workshops will be designed to be inclusive, interactive, and collaborative.
- Site visits: Stakeholders will be invited to visit the quarry site to see the project's implementation in person. This will provide an opportunity to address any concerns and answer questions that stakeholders may have o that may generate with time. In case they are working adequately as engagement activities, Tree Day Celebration and Open Doors Day for schoolchildren will be repeated.
- A scheduled meeting with the Valdilecha City Council, as well as one site visit for them to see the project's implementation in the site. Infographics will be created for local and regional authorities, showing the impact that quarrying has on the economy, as well as the improvements and advances that have been implemented to improve it.

- Simple informative activities will continue to be carried out to provide information about what is being done in the quarries to both internal and external stakeholders (using mailings, news, the website, etc.).

These activities will help ensure that the engagement plan remains effective and responsive to stakeholders' needs, making changes and adapting the activities when necessary.

4.3 Community Engagement Strategy – HOLCIM

Physical and socioeconomical context

The HOLCIM Pioltello San Bovio quarry is located in an area that has contact with three municipalities: Pioltello, Peschiera Borromeo, and Rodano. This means that the quarry's activities can potentially affect the lives and livelihoods of the residents in these municipalities; therefore, the Community Engagement Strategy must take into consideration the concerns and needs of not just one but multiple communities.

Each of the municipalities in the area has its own unique characteristics and challenges. Pioltello, for instance, has a large population density and a significant amount of green space, while Peschiera Borromeo has a strong productive ecosystem and a high rate of entrepreneurship. Rodano, on the other hand, is committed to agriculture and has important spring pools that are still active. It is important to engage with each of these municipalities to understand their specific concerns and needs related to the quarry's operations. The engagement strategy should be tailored so it includes each municipality, to ensure that their voices are heard, and their concerns are addressed.

Engaging with multiple municipalities can be a complex and challenging process. It requires a careful and strategic approach to ensure that each community feels included in the decision-making process. Therefore, the engagement strategy must be transparent, inclusive, and open to feedback from all stakeholders. On the other side of things, having contact with three different municipalities it can also be beneficial for the quarry, as it provides the opportunity to connect with a diverse range of people. This can allow for a more inclusive and comprehensive community engagement strategy that takes into account the various needs and perspectives of different groups. By engaging with a wider range of stakeholders, HOLCIM can work towards creating a more sustainable and mutually beneficial relationship with the surrounding communities.

Quarry workers

The quarry workers are a group of nine men, all over the age of 30. They have all received basic education, and possess varying levels of technological proficiency, with the majority having only a basic understanding of technology and a few having intermediate skills. Given that there are only a few workers, HOLCIM has the opportunity of giving a more personalized and individual training that can address their specific needs and skill levels.

In order to establish productive communication and engagement with the quarry workers, it will be essential to deliver accessible and comprehensible training and information using methods that are appropriate for their age and technical skills. Interactive workshops, training sessions, and practical demonstrations of the new technologies and equipment that will be implemented at the quarry may be included. Furthermore, frequent updates and feedback sessions will be conducted with the workers to ensure that they feel informed

and invested in the project. Addressing any issues or challenges they may face and providing assistance and guidance as necessary will also be critical.

Given the introduction of new technologies and improvements to the quarry because of the DEQ project, it is important that workers develop the necessary skills and have all the needed information and expertise to be prepared and adapt to these changes with ease. The changes in the quarry related to the project will particularly affect IT and maintenance processes, making it crucial that workers are equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills to operate these new systems safely and effectively. By investing in worker education and creating a culture of ongoing learning, the project can ensure that workers are empowered to succeed in their roles and contribute to the success of the quarry and their personal careers over the long term. Providing this training will also ensure that they are equipped with the skills and knowledge needed to effectively carry out their jobs and ensure greater safety through better human/machine interaction.

Objectives

Internal Stakeholders

- To ensure no resistance to change in the quarry and establish a communication pathway to prevent this from happening among employees.
- Provide training and resources to workers to prepare them for changes in their work processes resulting from the project.
- Consult and engage with workers to gather feedback and address any concerns they may have about the project.
- Collaborate with investors to ensure their needs and concerns are met.
- Keep clients and suppliers informed of project progress and any changes that may impact them.

External Stakeholders

- Collaborate and consult with local public administrations to ensure compliance with all relevant regulations and laws.
- Keep public administrations informed about the benefits of the project at local level and find synergies with development plans and strategies.
- Engage with local communities to inform them about the project, address any concerns they may have, and gather feedback.
- Build strong relationships with local communities and address their needs and concerns.
- Offer transparent and updated information about the project to CSOs.
- Inform and consult with quality/regulation associations about project results and engage them in consultation to standardise project results.
- Collaborate with the scientific community, inform them about project results and engage them in consultation to improve results implementation.

Community Engagement Strategy - HOLCIM

PHASE 1: CONSOLIDATION AND EXPLORATION PHASE

Internal Stakeholders

The community engagement plan for the DIGIECOQUARRY project includes various activities for both workers and other internal stakeholders. For workers, there will be regular updates on the project through internal communication channels, a dedicated site on HOLCIM's website, monthly updates, and training workshops. Additionally, feedback will be gathered from workers and a contact person will be provided for their questions and suggestions. For other internal stakeholders such as investors, clients, and suppliers, there will be collaboration and information-sharing about the benefits of DEQ in the final product, and updates on the project's progress.

Community Engagement activities for workers:

- Regular updates on the project during using the quarry's internal communication channels.
- Creation of a site within HOLCIM website dedicated to the project to offer regular updates about the project progress.
- Monthly updates of the project through mailing or post in the site.
- Training workshops/capacity building: training and resources to help workers understand new technologies or equipment that will be introduced as part of the project.
- Based on the monitoring strategy for the engagement strategy, establishing a system to gather feedback from workers, address any concerns they may have and ensure they feel valued and heard. Provision of a contact person in the site for questions and suggestions.

Community Engagement activities for other internal stakeholders:

- Collaboration with investors, informing about the benefits of DEQ for the future sustainability of the business activity, always aligned with their investment priorities.
- Clients will be informed about the benefits of DEQ in the final product, always aligned with their business priorities, using existing communication channels, such newsletters and mailing.
- Informing investors about the benefits of the projects during assemblies.
- Elaboration of a summary/document summarising the outcomes of the project, to be sent/presented to investors.
- Dedicated news on the quarry website for suppliers and other internal stakeholders.
- Update of the supplier policy document if necessary.

External stakeholders

HOLCIM's community engagement strategy for external stakeholders involves several activities tailored to specific groups. For local authorities, the quarry will consult and collaborate with them to keep them informed about the project's benefits and find synergies with development plans and strategies. Specific meetings, site visits, and open-door events will be scheduled. For local communities, direct communication will be established through easily understandable leaflets, open-door events, and a contact person for questions and suggestions. Open days will be held to create a first contact and invite them to continue participating in project activities. Finally, for other external stakeholders, HOLCIM will create a dedicated document/information in the sustainability section of its website and send mailings to identified scientific organizations and quality/regulation associations, to inform them about project results and engage them in consultation to improve and standardize them.

Community Engagement activities for Local Authorities:

- The quarry will consult and collaborate with the public administrations, keeping them informed about the benefits of the project at the local level and finding synergies with development plans and strategies.
- A dedicated dossier with information about the project will be developed.
- Specific Meeting, site visits and open-door events will be scheduled for local authorities.

Community Engagement activities for Local Communities:

- The quarry will consult and collaborate with the local communities, keeping them informed about the benefits of the project at local level.
- Finding synergies with development plans and strategies.
- Direct communication through dedicated leaflets with easily understandable language and open-door events.
- Provision of a contact person for questions and suggestions (form on the website).
- Publication of a news article in the regional media to inform the local communities about the DIGIECOQUARRY project.

Open days will be of special importance to make a first contact with the local community. These events will be used to talk about what aspects that interest or concern them the most, as well as to create a first contact and invite them to continue participating in the activities that will continue to be carried out.

Community Engagement activities for other external stakeholders:

- Create a dedicated document/information in the sustainability section of the corporate website to offer transparent and updated information about the project to CSOs.
- Mailings to identified scientific organizations to inform about project results and engage them in consultation to improve results implementation.

- Mailing to identified quality/regulation associations to inform about project results and engage them in consultation to standardise them.

PHASE 2: CO-CREATION AND DEEPENING PHASE

The second phase of the community engagement strategy aims to deepen the relationship with stakeholders and foster a sense of ownership and commitment to the project's success.

The aim of the second phase is to build upon the engagement activities that were conducted and monitored in the first one. The relationships formed with stakeholders during phase one will make it easier to involve them in this next stage, as well as to encourage their participation. Co-creation workshops will be organized to allow stakeholders to give their feedback and ideas in an interactive and inclusive way, which could be especially enriching considering the many citizens HOLCIM could have access to by carrying out an effective engagement plan.

The following activities will continue to be implemented, although they will be subject to feedback and success rates from the first phase, and adjustments will be made based on lessons learned.

- Co-creation workshops: Stakeholders will be invited to participate in workshops where they can share their ideas and feedback. These workshops will be designed to be inclusive, interactive, and collaborative, and will include stakeholders from the three municipalities near the quarry.
- Site visits: Stakeholders (especially citizens and local authorities) will be invited to visit the quarry site to see the project's implementation in person, as well as the changes and improvements of the quarry over time and beyond the project. This will provide an opportunity to address any concerns and answer questions that stakeholders may have or that may generate with time.
- Stakeholder meetings: two meetings a year will be held with stakeholders to keep them informed about the project's progress and address any new concerns or issues that may arise. In this case, discussions will be held with stakeholders to try to structure these meetings.
- Simple informative activities will continue to be carried out to provide information about what is being done in the quarries to both internal and external stakeholders, especially with CSOs, citizen associations and scientific organizations.

These activities will help ensure that the engagement plan remains effective and responsive to stakeholders' needs.

4.4 Community Engagement Strategy – CSI

Physical and socioeconomical context

The village of Mammendorf, with a population of about 250, is located near the CSI quarry. The quarry is the largest economic enterprise in the area and is situated only 150 meters away from the village. The quarrying of andesite represents a significant intervention in the cultural landscape of the Magdeburger Börde, and has the potential to negatively impact the environment, including noise, dust, and blast vibrations. Therefore, it is

important to establish and maintain good relationships with the local community, particularly as their quality of life can be affected by the quarry's operations. With the agricultural sector being the dominant industry in the region, and the soil being one of the best in Germany, it is essential to ensure that any quarrying activities are carried out in a sustainable and responsible manner. This will require engaging with the community and addressing their concerns, while also implementing measures to mitigate the environmental impact of the quarry.

The quarry in Mammendorf also offers a rich record of geological, paleontological, and archaeological evidence that spans millions of years. It provides valuable insights into the history of the region and the evolution of life on earth. The quarry has revealed sediments with several hundred species of marine fauna and other prehistoric finds, including fossils from before the existence of the North Sea. Archeological discoveries range from the middle Neolithic period to the Iron Age, including a woman's burial from the Middle Bronze Age and evidence of prehistoric settlements. All of these discoveries could be enriching and interesting to include in the community engagement strategy, as they help educate and engage the public with the rich history and natural wonders of the region.

One important aspect to consider in this situation is the role of public authorities. As the quarry has been facing challenges in obtaining permits and approval for their operations, it is crucial to maintain open communication with the relevant authorities and demonstrate the positive impact of the project and the quarry's operations. It is also important to highlight the potential negative effects of halting the quarry's activity, such as economic consequences for the community and potential environmental issues if the quarry site is not properly maintained. Building a strong relationship with public authorities can help ensure the quarry's continued operation while also addressing any concerns or issues that may arise.

Quarry workers

The quarry workers at the CSI facility in Mammendorf are a diverse group, with ages ranging from young apprentices to more experienced veterans. Currently they have 45 workers, 39 male and 6 female, and the majority of them have completed apprenticeships as their highest level of education. It is important to ensure that these workers are properly trained and equipped with the necessary skills to handle the changes brought by the project.

While they will require training to adapt to new digital tools, the quarry is already highly automated, so the workers are already well-adapted to the existing level of automation and digitization. It is worth noting that the implementation of the changes in the project is not expected to result in significant changes to the workers' job status. While digitization has the potential to increase efficiency, it will not necessarily result in a reduction in the number of workers required. The quarry has already assigned one employee to the role of fleet manager, indicating a commitment to optimizing operations while maintaining a strong workforce.

Despite the specific circumstances of the quarry and its automation, the workers remain the most important internal stakeholder group. It is crucial to keep them in mind throughout the project and to ensure that they are fully informed and trained on any changes that may occur.

Objectives

Internal Stakeholders

- To ensure no resistance to change in the quarry and to establish a communication pathway to prevent this from happening among employees.
- Provide training and resources to workers to prepare them for changes in their work processes that may result from the project.
- Inform and consult workers to gather feedback and address any concerns they may have about the project.
- Collaborate with investors to ensure their needs and concerns are met.
- Keep clients and suppliers informed of project progress and any changes that may impact them.

External Stakeholders

- Engage with public authorities to showcase the benefits of the project and the quarry in order to facilitate permit acquisition and ensure the continuity of the quarry's operations.
- Collaborate and consult with local public administrations to ensure compliance with all relevant regulations and laws.
- Keep public administrations informed about the benefits of the project at local level and find synergies with development plans and strategies.
- Collaborate with local communities to inform them about the project, address any concerns they may have, and gather feedback.
- Maintain strong relationships with local communities and address their needs and concerns.
- Inform about the project and its impact in the territory, engage CSOs in increasing benefits for the community and avoid opposition to the project.
- Engage the scientific community, inform them about project results and engage them in consultation to improve results implementation.

Community Engagement Strategy - CSI

PHASE 1: CONSOLIDATION AND EXPLORATION PHASE

Internal Stakeholders

Despite the level of automation and technology at the CSI quarry prior to the project, the workers remain the most important internal stakeholder group. Therefore, CSI will implement community engagement activities specifically designed to keep their workers informed and involved by providing regular updates on the project and will make training workshops and resources available to help workers understand any new technologies or equipment introduced as part of the project.

For other internal stakeholders such as investors, clients, and suppliers, the engagement activities include informal meetings, summaries of project outcomes, and regular mailing updates to inform them about the benefits of the project.

Community Engagement activities for workers:

- Regular updates of the project for employees via the company's communication channels.
- 1 project site available on the CSI website.
- Training workshops/capacity building: training and resources to help workers understand new technologies or equipment that will be introduced as part of the project.
- Based on the monitoring strategy for the engagement strategy, establishing a system to gather feedback from workers, address any concerns they may have and ensure they feel valued and heard.

Community Engagement activities for other internal stakeholders:

- An informal meeting with investors to identify their expectations about the DIGIECOQUARRY project.
- Elaboration of a summary/document summarising the outcomes of the project, to be sent and/or presented to investors.
- Clients will be informed about the benefits of DEQ in short news or messages to inform about the participation in the project.
- For suppliers, elaboration of a short message to be included in mailing to inform them about the project.

External stakeholders

The quarry operation has a significant impact on the surrounding community and the local authorities are responsible for granting permits and monitoring compliance with regulations. To maintain a positive relationship with local authorities, CSI will communicate effectively with them about the benefits of the DIGIECOQUARRY project and the improvements in safety and environmental impact that it will bring. CSI will also be proactive in addressing any concerns that local authorities may have and will provide regular updates on its progress.

Community Engagement activities for Local Authorities:

- Elaboration of a communication dossier, with specific information of projects' impact in the territory.
- Inform public authorities about the project.
- Organisation of a site visit for public authorities to see project's implementation in the site and answer their questions.

Community Engagement activities for Local Communities:

- Elaboration of a leaflet or postcard explaining the project.
- Contact local communities to be informed about the project.
- Publication of one news in local/regional media.

PHASE 2: CO-CREATION AND DEEPENING PHASE

The second phase of the community engagement strategy aims to deepen the relationship with all stakeholders, both internal and external, and foster a sense of ownership and commitment to the success of the CSI quarry operation. The goal is to deepen the relationship with stakeholders, particularly local authorities, and foster a sense of ownership and commitment to the success of the quarry operation. During this phase, CSI will engage in close collaboration with stakeholders to co-create solutions that address their needs and concerns, while keeping a special focus on the local authorities, which have a critical role in granting necessary permits.

At the same time, CSI will also begin to establish a more meaningful dialogue with the citizens once the groundwork has been laid in the first phase. Activities such as site visits may be planned to involve them in the decision-making process and address their concerns. Overall, the second phase of the community engagement strategy will allow for a more inclusive and collaborative approach, ensuring the long-term success of the CSI quarry operation.

- Stakeholder meetings: Regular meetings will be held with stakeholders to keep them informed about the project's progress and address any new concerns or issues that may arise. In this case, discussions will be held with stakeholders to try to structure these meetings.
- Simple informative activities will continue to be carried out to provide information about what is being done in the quarries to both internal and external stakeholders, especially with CSOs, citizen associations and scientific organizations.

These activities will help ensure that the engagement plan remains effective and responsive to stakeholders' needs.

4.5 Community Engagement Strategy – CIMPOR

Physical and socioeconomical context

The CIMPOR pilot site is located in Alenquer, a Portuguese municipality belonging to the district of Lisbon, integrating the Intermunicipal Community of the West in the Central region of Portugal, and it has a population of approximately 43,267 people spread across 11 parishes. The area is known for its hillside layout, earning the nickname "Portugal's Nativity Scene." The municipality has a rich history and heritage, with prehistoric sites, castles, convents, churches, and stately homes. Agriculture, particularly vineyards and wine production, is a major economic activity in the county. As the municipality is positioned in relation to the Lisbon Metropolitan Area, it has experienced urban expansion in recent years. This information could be relevant for the community engagement strategy, as it provides a glimpse into the local economy and cultural heritage, which may be important to consider when engaging with stakeholders.

To maintain positive social relationships with the surrounding communities, CIMPOR takes measures to measure and report dust emissions, ground vibration, and noise on an annual basis. Additionally, the company performs archaeological surveys when opening new excavation fronts to protect the cultural heritage of the surrounding area.

Quarry workers

CIMPOR's quarry workers are all local, with 100% of the workforce coming from the surrounding communities. Many of the workers and their families live in close proximity to the quarry, highlighting the importance of maintaining positive social relationships with the local communities. The workforce consists of 19 male and 1 female employees, with a range of educational levels, with most having a basic or high school education. The age range of the workers is fairly broad, with the majority falling between 45-50 years old.

CIMPOR places a strong emphasis on providing internal upskilling programs and trainings for their workers, with a primary focus on health and safety issues. In addition to these trainings, employees also receive training on driving mobile equipment, languages, leadership, and software used within the company. Workers are regularly specialized in health, safety, risk, and environmental issues.

Moving forward, CIMPOR plans to continue providing internal trainings and upskilling programs for their workers while also implementing new trainings to ensure they are prepared for changes related to DEQ. The company will also maintain their focus on maintaining positive social relationships with the surrounding communities through continued measurement and reporting of their impact and cultural heritage protection efforts.

Objectives

Internal Stakeholders

- To ensure no resistance to change in the quarry and establish a communication pathway to prevent this from happening among employees.
- Provide training and resources to workers to prepare them for changes in their work processes resulting from the project.
- Consult and engage with workers to gather feedback and address any concerns they may have about the project.
- Involve clients and inform them about the benefits of DIGIECOQUARRY's final product.
- Inform investors about the benefits of the project for the future sustainability of the business activity.
- Inform suppliers about the project and potential new sustainability requirements that may be required from them.

External Stakeholders

- Involve public administrations and keep them informed about the benefits of the project at local, regional and national level and find synergies with development plans and strategies.
- Consult local communities and inform them about the project and potential impacts and start a bi-directional communication process.
- Build strong relationships with local communities and address their needs and concerns.

- Inform CSOs by offering transparent and updated information about the project.

Community Engagement Strategy - CIMPOR

PHASE 1: CONSOLIDATION AND EXPLORATION PHASE

Internal Stakeholders

Through the activities in phase 1, CIMPOR aims to have strong engagement with its internal stakeholders, with a particular focus on its workers. Various engagement strategies will be implemented to keep workers informed and engaged throughout the project and beyond. This includes creating a dedicated site for the project with regular updates, giving them monthly updates via mailing and having training workshops and resources to help workers understand new technologies and equipment.

For other internal stakeholders, such as investors, clients, and suppliers, CIMPOR will elaborate a summary/document to be sent or presented to investors, a short news or message to inform clients of the project's participation, and a news/update on the project for suppliers.

Community Engagement activities for workers:

- Creation of a site dedicated to the project to offer regular updates.
- Monthly updates of the project using mailing or post in the site.
- Training workshops/capacity building: training and resources to help workers understand new technologies or equipment that will be introduced as part of the project.
- Creation of a mailbox or communication channel in the site for questions and suggestions.

Community Engagement activities for other internal stakeholders:

- Elaboration of a summary/document summarising the outcomes of the project, to be sent/presented to investors.
- Elaboration of a short news or message to inform about clients the participation in the project to be sent as part of regular mailings and to be used by commercial staff when communicating with clients.
- Elaboration of a news/update on the project and sustainability objectives for suppliers and elaboration of a short message to be included in a mail.

External stakeholders

Through these Community Engagement activities, CIMPOR will have direct contact with external stakeholders. The activities aim to provide specific information about the project and the quarry's impact in the territory and to answer any questions or concerns that may arise. CIMPOR will have the opportunity to showcase the

project's implementation through site visits and the publication of news in local/regional media. By appointing a local community relations manager and creating a contact point on its website, CIMPOR will ensure that citizens have access to accurate and transparent information about the project and its new extraction techniques. Overall, these activities will help to establish a positive and constructive relationship between CIMPOR and its external stakeholders.

Community Engagement activities for Local Authorities:

- Elaboration of a communication dossier, with specific information of projects' impact in the territory.
- Organisation of a meeting with public authorities to inform about the project and answer their questions.
- Organisation of a site visit for public authorities to see project's implementation in the site.

Community Engagement activities for Local Communities:

- Elaboration of a leaflet or postcard explaining the project and new extraction techniques.
- Appoint a local community relations manager to engage with citizens.
- Creation of a contact point for questions and suggestions in the CIMPOR website.
- Publication of one news in local/regional media.

PHASE 2: CO-CREATION AND DEEPENING PHASE

The second stage of the community engagement strategy is aimed at strengthening relationships with stakeholders. In this phase, CIMPOR will collaborate closely with stakeholders to co-create solutions that address their needs and concerns.

The goal of this phase is to build on the engagement initiatives and activities that were implemented and monitored in the first phase. The connections that were established with stakeholders during phase one will make it easier to involve them in this phase and encourage their participation. Co-creative workshops will enable stakeholders to share their opinions and ideas in an interactive and inclusive manner.

The following activities will continue to be implemented, albeit subject to feedback and success rates from the first phase. Adjustments will be made based on lessons learned.

- Co-creative workshops: Stakeholders will be invited to attend workshops where they can express their opinions and give feedback. These workshops will be collaborative, interactive, and inclusive.
- Site visits: Stakeholders (especially citizens and local authorities) will be asked to visit the quarry to witness the project's execution in person and the quarry's changes and improvements over time and beyond the project's scope. This will present an opportunity to address any concerns and answer any questions that stakeholders may have.
- Stakeholder meetings: Meetings will be held regularly with stakeholders to keep them informed about the project's progress and address any new issues or concerns that may arise. In this scenario, discussions will be conducted with stakeholders to attempt to schedule these meetings several times a year, if feasible.

- Simple informative activities will continue to be conducted to provide information on the quarry's operations to both internal and external stakeholders, such as information through leaflets, mailing and short news on the quarry website.

These activities will help ensure that the engagement plan continues to be effective and responsive to the needs of stakeholders.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this document outlines the Citizen Engagement Strategy for the quarries involved in the DEQ project. The strategies include a variety of activities that are tailored to the local community and aimed at promoting dialogue, transparency, and trust between the quarry and the community.

Furthermore, to ensure the achievement of the CES goals in each pilot site all the engagement strategies of each quarry are based on their own relationship dynamics with stakeholders which have been built throughout the life of the quarries. Thus, when needed, the CES developed under DEQ will complement and formalize the already existing engagement actions in structured plans with monitoring indicators. This monitoring process along with the lessons learned and best practices that will be obtained at the end of the project, and which will be included in D7.5, will allow the quarries to continue engaging with their stakeholders effectively and to improve their strategies and activities.

It is also important to note that the Citizen Engagement Strategy is not a one-time event but an ongoing process that requires sustained effort and commitment. Therefore, this document also provides guidance on how to ensure the continuation of the engagement beyond the life of the DEQ project. This will enable the quarries to continue to engage with the community effectively and to adapt their strategies and activities as needed. In this way, the Citizen Engagement Strategy provides a framework for sustainable engagement that benefits both the quarries and the communities in which they operate. The two-phase approach presented in the document also provides a clear roadmap for the quarries to follow, which will help them to track their progress and make necessary adjustments to their engagement activities.

It is worth noting that this Citizen Engagement Strategy also considers the importance of engaging with internal stakeholders, such as employees. The engagement activities proposed in the document aim to foster a culture of social responsibility within the company and wants to ensure that workers have the necessary training to adequately adapt to the changes brought about by the project at all times.

By implementing the Citizen Engagement Strategy proposed in this document, the quarries can build stronger relationships with their stakeholders, enhance their social awareness and community understanding of raw materials, and promote sustainable quarrying practices.

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